

Initial challenges and approach for life cycle sustainability assessment in upcycling of PE and PET

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Plastic and Bioplastics

upPE-T project

Life Cycle Assessment

Plastics are everywhere in products as simple as paperclips or as complex as planes. Due to their versatility, plastics are causing many problems in terms of **waste** and pollution.

Many solutions have been placed to get rid of the plastic waste, such as mechanical or chemical processes.

Bioplastics are a promising alternative,
but they are still expensive and not
widely available.
The progressive substitution of consumer
products derived from fossil fuels is
crucial **to decarbonise** our society,
especially in short shelf life packaging

What if an alternative exists?

This is **upPE-T**, in which a novel **upcycling** process to transform PE and PET waste into bioplastics is developing.

OVERVIEW OF BIOTECHNOLOGICAL PRODUCTION OF BIOPLASTIC PHBV

But a **sustainable process** that is environmentally, economically, and socially sound is needed.

Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment (LCSA) is a combination of environmental (LCA), economic (LCC) and social aspects (sLCA) assessment

Life Cycle Inventory

Data can be obtained by:

Directly
collected

Database

Literature
data

The databases

LCC

sLCA

Life Cycle Costing and social Life Cycle Assessment

Why perform LCSA is so challenging?

Gate to gate

Building customised processes

Assumptions

Split the analysis

Our
approach

Why is needed to perform the LCSEA from the beginning?

Thank you for the attention!

Find out more on <http://https://uppet.eu/> or feel free to collect a brochure from me!